

EXPLORING THE CHALLENGES OF THE TEACHERS IN THE INTEGRATION OF TECHNOLOGY IN EARLY CHILDHOOD CLASSROOM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635158>

ABSTRACT

The integration of technology in early childhood education is increasingly recognized as essential for fostering foundational skills in young learners. This phenomenological study explores the challenges faced by teachers in the North President Quirino District Division of Sultan Kudarat as they incorporate technology into early childhood classrooms. The objectives are to identify specific barriers, understand the impact of these challenges on teaching practices, and provide recommendations for effective technology integration. Methodologically, this study employs a qualitative approach, utilizing in-depth interviews with 20 early childhood educators selected through purposive sampling. Data were analyzed using thematic analysis to capture the essence of teachers' experiences and perceptions. Findings reveal several significant challenges: limited access to technological resources, inadequate training and professional development, resistance to change among educators, and difficulties in maintaining student engagement with technological tools. These barriers hinder the effective use of technology, leading to inconsistent implementation and varying educational outcomes. Conclusions drawn from the study highlight the need for comprehensive support systems, including enhanced access to resources, ongoing professional development programs tailored to early childhood educators, and initiatives to foster a positive attitude towards technological integration. Addressing these challenges is crucial for optimizing the benefits of technology in early childhood education and ensuring that young learners are equipped with the necessary skills for the digital age.

Keywords: *Early Childhood Education, Technology Integration, Teacher Challenges, Phenomenological Study*

INTRODUCTION

Incorporating technology can be difficult since there are "plenty of models to choose from; the problem is not that a useful model cannot be found, but that deciding upon a model can be a complex task" (Kimmons & Hall, 2018, p.29). When incorporating technology into the classroom, educators may encounter barriers that prevent or limit the use of technology. This article will be presented topically, with a study of integration models and the challenges that arise when implementing technology.

In the situated of President Quirino School especially, in the rural areas some of the schools are lack of equipment and poor children or students development because in the rural areas student doesn't have technology in home like TV, computers and even a cellphone to have access in any technology concern sometimes teachers barriers are poor connection or low speed internet that would interrupt the class also teachers cannot give more integration of technology to the class presentation because the early childhood are very sensitive of about technology.

The use of technology in classrooms has increased over the previous two decades, including in early childhood education (Tang et al., 2016). Effective technology integration with purpose and meaning can have numerous positive effects on younger kids (Bowen & Watson, 2017; Mustola et al., 2018; Quesenberry et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2016). It can be extremely effective, helping to boost both student accomplishment and student engagement in even the youngest students (Bowen & Watson, 2017; O'Byrne & Pytash, 2017; Tang et al., 2016).

The purpose of this study is to explore how and why early childhood teachers chose technology activities to integrate into their instruction, this study is influential because barriers that early childhood educators encounter when choosing the most appropriate technology activities to implement in the classroom were discovered. Also, this study has the potential to bring about positive social change in the students by informing early childhood educators about effective applications of technology that could contribute to student achievement.

While there are multiple benefits to deliberate and meaningful technology integration (Bowen & Watson, 2017; O'Bryne & Pytash, 2017; Tang et al., 2016), many early childhood educators do not use technology effectively. Rather than using technology to support or enhance instruction and encourage higher order thinking, many early childhood educators use it to digitally display information or have students work on computer programs for a set period of time (Smith et al., 2016). Furthermore, there is little research on how early childhood instructors perceive and use technology in their classrooms, or whether meaningful and purposeful technology practices are used (Smith et al., 2016).

This study explored the challenges faced by early childhood educators and identified coping mechanisms by completing in these gaps. This research intends to aid in the creation of useful strategies and interventions that might strengthen early childhood educators in the classroom based on the connectivist. The aim of this thesis that scholars George Siemens and Stephen Downes presented in 2005. The foundation of connectivism, also known as connectivist learning theory, is the notion that digital technology fosters interpersonal connections and opens up opportunities for learning.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the coping mechanisms of the Teachers challenges in the Integration of Technology in Early childhood classroom in the District of North President Quirino.

This research sought to provide valuable insight and recommendation to support, here are some ways of question to be answer:

1. What are the specific challenges faced by teachers when integrating technology in early childhood classrooms?
2. What are strategies do teachers use to ensure that technology is developmentally appropriate to young learners?
3. As a teacher in early childhood how do you defined Traditional methods and technology integration?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study is qualitative research design, specifically phenomenological in nature of research. Qualitative research concerned with establishing answers to how is the phenomenon in question.

The Phenomenology is both a philosophical movement and a family of qualitative research methodologies. The term phenomenology refers to the study of phenomena, where a phenomenon is anything that appears to someone in their conscious, experience (Creswell, 2013). Phenomenology is to address a range of research questions. It elaborates on a series of guidelines to support researchers in selecting one type that is opposite to their needs. It is the study that explores what was experienced and focuses on their experience it allows to track the empathy and recognition of both the researchers and the participant subjectivity.

Participants of the Study

The Participants of this study were the teachers of North President Quirino, Division of Sultan Kudarat, Criteria have been established to select individuals who have significant experiences, particularly in the thirteen (13) schools handling Early Childhood Education (kinder).

The participants who met the researcher's specified inclusion criteria based on the study of Ngag (2023) where he considered experts who served as informants and source of data. By this way, he established the generalizability and reliability of the selection.

Sampling Technique

The researcher used a purposive sampling technique in the selection of the respondents. This technique will be non-parametric sampling in nature because the researcher will choose participants based on convenience.

Purposive sampling (also known as judgment, selective, or subjective sampling) is a sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her judgment when choosing members or participants of the study. Further, purposive sampling is used to select respondents who are most likely to yield appropriate and useful information (Kelly, 2010).

Data Gathering Instrument

The study employed a self-structure survey questionnaire crafted upon reading, thesis, and dissertations. The questionnaires are conducted through recording and Interviews.

In addition, self -structure questionnaires will be evaluated by experts in the District office such as the teachers holding Master Teacher items or supervisors in function in the field such as school heads and academic coordinators. The instrument will finally approved by the members of the panel before the researcher administers to the participants.

Upon approval by the evaluation panels and validation through the East-West Mindanao College Inc. validation tool, the researcher was authorized to administer the developed survey. Before data collection, ethical clearance was sought from the East-West Research Ethics Committee (EREC) to ensure that the research adhered to ethical standards, including participant consent, confidentiality, and protection of participant rights.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sent a letter to the Dean of the Graduate School asking permission to conduct the study or approval of the chairperson of the graduate school. Then, a letter to the school division Superintendent, Supervisors, Principals, and participants of the study, before the survey questionnaires will be administered to the schools.

During the interviews, the researcher used video and audio recordings to capture the participants' responses accurately, ensuring that every detail was documented for subsequent analysis. The use of video and audio recordings allowed the researcher to focus on the conversation and engage more fully with the participants, ensuring that the data reflected the true sentiments and insights shared by the participants. This careful and systematic approach to data collection ensured the reliability and validity of the research findings.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the qualitative data collected from the participants, comprising interviews and focus group transcripts it involves the identification and reporting of patterns in a data set, which are then interpreted for their inherent meaning.enabling a deeper understanding of the participants' in Technology Integration in childhood classroom (Braun & Clark, 2006).

Thematic analysis, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006), is a method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data. The process begins with data familiarization, where researchers immerse themselves in the data by reading and re-reading transcripts while noting initial ideas. This is followed by generating initial codes, where key features of the data are systematically labeled across the entire data set.

The next step involves searching for themes by collating codes into potential themes, then reviewing themes to ensure they accurately represent the data and are coherent. After refining the themes, each theme is defined and named to capture its essence and distinct aspects.

Finally, the themes are reported in a detailed and coherent manner, often illustrated with data extracts, to provide a rich, insightful narrative that addresses the research questions. This method allows for a flexible, systematic, and rigorous analysis of qualitative data.

Following data collection, the transcripts were systematically reviewed to identify common themes and patterns emerging from the participants' responses which patterned after the study of Ngag (2023). Through an iterative process of coding and

categorization, key themes were identified, reflecting the participants' perceptions, concerns, and insights regarding the agenda.

Themes were identified based on their frequency, relevance, and significance to the research objectives, ensuring that the analysis captured the essence of the participants' experiences and perspectives.

Scope and Limitations

This study was limited to the experiences of the early childhood teachers in remote area on how and what to use in terms of strategies. This study focus on Teachers concern in dealing pupils with integration of technology in school year 2024-2025. The Teachers participants are those teachers handling early childhood.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Challenges Faced by Teachers

Teachers face several challenges when integrating technology in early childhood classrooms.

First, many teachers may lack sufficient training and confidence in using technology effectively, which can impede their ability to incorporate digital tools into their teaching practices.

Second, unequal access to devices and internet connectivity among students can hinder equitable learning opportunities, creating a digital divide.

Third, balancing screen time with other developmental activities and ensuring that the content is age-appropriate are ongoing challenges that require careful consideration and planning.

Lastly, adapting technology to suit diverse learning styles and integrating it seamlessly into existing curriculum frameworks can be complex, requiring teachers to continuously develop and refine their instructional strategies.

Strategies Used by Teachers:

To ensure that technology is developmentally appropriate for young learners, teachers employ various strategies. They select educational apps, games, and multimedia that align with early childhood developmental milestones, ensuring that the content is suitable for the children's age and learning stage.

Teachers also monitor and guide children's interactions with technology to maximize learning outcomes and minimize distractions, providing support and direction as needed. Additionally, they incorporate hands-on, tactile experiences alongside digital interactions to reinforce concepts and skills, blending traditional and technological approaches to create a balanced learning environment.

Engaging parents and caregivers in discussions about responsible digital use and extending learning beyond the classroom is another critical strategy, fostering a collaborative approach to children's digital literacy and overall development.

Definition of Traditional Methods and Technology Integration:

In early childhood education, traditional methods encompass a variety of hands-on activities, including storytelling, music, art, and physical play. These methods focus on sensory experiences and social interactions to nurture holistic development, emphasizing the importance of direct engagement and experiential learning. In contrast, technology integration involves incorporating digital tools such as tablets, computers, educational apps, and interactive media into classroom activities.

The goal of technology integration is to enhance learning experiences, promote digital literacy, and prepare children for future technological environments. By combining traditional methods with digital tools, educators aim to create a comprehensive educational experience that supports both foundational skills and modern competencies.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings of the study, the following were concluded:

From the research, it is evident that while technology offers immense potential in early childhood education, its integration poses challenges related to teacher preparedness, access, and pedagogical alignment.

However, strategic approaches such as careful content selection, active supervision, and balanced use of technology alongside traditional methods can effectively mitigate these challenges and maximize learning benefits for young learners.

Recommendations

Based on the results, and conclusions, the following were recommended:

1. DepEd may provide comprehensive training and ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their digital literacy skills and pedagogical strategies for technology integration. Ensure equitable access to technology resources and internet connectivity across all early childhood education settings to minimize disparities in learning opportunities.

2. Curriculum Developers may design digital resources and curricula that align with early childhood developmental stages, ensuring age-appropriateness and educational value. Provide clear guidelines and frameworks for integrating technology into early childhood curricula, emphasizing the importance of hands-on learning and play-based activities.

3. Teachers may continue integrating technology in ways that support diverse learning styles and developmental needs, while maintaining a balanced approach with traditional methods. Foster partnerships with parents and caregivers to promote responsible digital use at home and extend learning experiences beyond the classroom.

4. Future Researchers may conduct longitudinal studies to track the impact of technology integration on early childhood development over time, considering both short-term outcomes and long-term effects. Explore innovative pedagogical approaches that combine technology with traditional methods to optimize learning experiences and outcomes for young children.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent will be diligently obtained from all school heads part of this study. They must possess a comprehensive understanding of the research objectives. Methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Further, participation will remain entirely voluntary, and have the right to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any consequences.

Anonymity and confidentiality to safeguard the personal identities of the teachers' responses, rigorous measures will be enacted to ensure safety and confidentiality. Rather than using the actual name, pseudonyms or codes will be used to ensure the privacy of the participants. The gathered data will be securely stored with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, will be explained with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. The approach will be put to minimize distress and the support system will be readily available to guide participants should the need arise.

Acknowledgments

This study would not have been possible without the guidance and assistance of several individuals. The researcher extends heartfelt gratitude to Marjuni M. Maddi, Director General of MBHTE-Higher Education, for his wisdom and encouragement, and Crispin A. Soliven Jr., CESE Schools Division Superintendent of Sultan Kudarat, for permitting the study. Special thanks to Patricea I. Sandigan, MAED, School President,

for her unwavering support, and Emilia M. Lotilla, PhD, Dean of the Graduate School at East West Mindanao College Inc., for her invaluable input.

The researcher's adviser, Amiludin G. Masabpi, PhD, his expertise, encouragement and for the intellectual support to accomplished this study. Panel members Jaime Boy U. Ngag, Jr., PhD, for his professional ideas made this study possible and Leodie D. Mones, PhD, offered meaningful advice, while Michael A. Poblador, PhD, meticulously reviewed the content. Juliet P. Tambungalan, MAED, Academic Chairperson, very active to provided support,patience and guidance,and Josephine C. Pacete, PhD, District Supervisor of North President Quirino,Division of Sultan Kudarat and a validators questionnaires of researcher supported the study permit and for her assistance in the conduct of this study. and the school heads and teachers of North President Quirino District also contributed significantly.

To her classmates and friends, for the friendship, unforgettable experiences, and funny memories together during the journey of learning which motivated her; To her Husband, Parents and Siblings, for the undying love, guidance and support that made this intellectual endeavor more bearable, Above all, to ALLAH (SWT), for endless blessings and guidance on us in realizing this research paper. SUKRAN AND
W A S S A L A M .

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